

DIFFERENCES IN ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT BASED ON PERSONALITY TYPE OF MARKETING EMPLOYEES OF PT. BANK BTPN LUBUK PAKAM

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Abstract

Marketing employee organizational commitment is needed by the company because marketing employees play a role in the progress of the company. With high commitment, employees will find goals in fulfilling the organization's mission. Individual personality characteristics are one of the factors that influence an employee's organizational commitment. There are two personality types owned by individuals, namely extroverted personalities who have a positive and open attitude while introverted personalities have attitudes that are difficult to adjust to, lack self-confidence and are more closed to their social environment. This study aims to determine differences in organizational commitment in terms of personality types of employees at PT. Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang, using reference to Carl Jung's theory in Feist and Robert, 2018. This research method is a non-experimental quantitative study with survey techniques and questionnaires as data collection instruments. Data analysis used is the T-test. The results showed that there was a difference in organizational commitment with the extrovert personality type = 192.706 and organizational commitment with the introvert personality type = 160.061.

Keywords: Extrovert, Introvert, Personality, Organizational Commitment.

INTRODUCTION DAN LITERATURE REVIEW

Nowadays, one of the strategies in improving business competition is human resource management. Human resources (HR) are a major part of company activities, one of which is marketing employees. Marketing employees in the organization have a very important role because they are the main driving force in organizational production (Fitri Anggreani, 2021). Satisfying and stable production results are also influenced by the good organizational commitment of each marketing employee (Bae, 2023). An organization has a goal to achieve excellence, both excellence to compete with other organizations and to maintain the organization. In achieving this excellence, it must increase commitment to individual employees because basically employee commitment will affect team performance and will ultimately affect overall organizational performance (Karlinda et al., 2022).

Organizational commitment is the core of an organization, where this commitment will determine employees' interest in the organization where they work and will ultimately decide whether employees want to stay and develop in advancing the organization's mission or even prefer to other more promising organizations (Muktamar & Saputra, 2024). The characteristics of employees who are committed to the organization include having initiative, having a strong sense of attachment to the organization, a sense of employee involvement (loyalty), having a

clear vision, working earnestly, and self-awareness of responsibilities in the organization Goleman (in Wijaya and Rifa'i, 2016). The commitment of each employee is different, this difference may be due to the three aspects of organizational commitment, including affective commitment, namely employees who have a high emotional bond to the company where they work, this emotional bond is formed because there is a sense of job satisfaction within the employee (Kurniawan, 2022), so that the employee really has a desire to stay in the company where he works, then continuous commitment, namely employees who have an awareness of the advantages and disadvantages if the employee leaves the company where he works. The profit and loss can be seen from how much the employee invests in the company and if he leaves the company the employee will experience a loss, so that the employee has a need to stay in the company (Farrukh et al, 2017) .

In this regard, the individual cannot be expected to have a strong desire to contribute to the organization. On the other hand, there is normative commitment, namely employees who have a commitment that looks at existing norms, if the employee leaves the company, the employee will feel inappropriate because he has a feeling bond to the tasks in the company where he works. With employee commitment, it is expected that all work will run effectively (Sakti et al., 2023). A high level of commitment will create high morale. The quality and quantity of work will be better and will be completed on time. The higher the level of organizational commitment in employees, the higher the level of work results and will affect the faster achievement of company goals. If the lower the level of organizational commitment in employees, the lower the work results of employees in a company.

Spector (2013), an employee who has a commitment to the organization is an employee who has involvement in an organization because an employee who has a high commitment, the employee will find a goal in the organization's mission and will actively seek opportunities to fulfill the organization's mission. With the existence of organizational commitment in marketing employees, it is expected that all work will run effectively. The higher the level of organizational commitment in employees, the higher the level of work results and will affect the achievement of company goals. If the lower the level of organizational commitment in employees, the lower the work results of employees in a company. This will affect the slow achievement of company goals which will harm the company and the employees themselves.

Minner in Darmadi (2018) there are factors that influence the organizational commitment of an employee, including the personal characteristics of the individual which includes the personality of the individual himself, because that personality will affect the progress of the company, which will affect the attitudes of employees towards their work.

This attitude will determine the employee's commitment to the work assigned and the success of an employee at work is determined by his personality factors. Feist & Robert (2018) state that personality is every individual who includes extroverts and introverts. Extroverted personality types have the characteristics of individuals who are positive and open to their environment. While the introverted personality type has the characteristics of individuals who are difficult to adjust and do not easily get along with the environment around them.

Therefore, marketing employees are burdened with high enough targets that will determine whether employees will remain in the organization or prefer to switch to other companies that are more promising and reviewed according to the personality type of each employee. Personality is a person's way of acting and interacting with others, meaning that personality itself is something that arises from the individual in determining the attitude taken in dealing with certain situations so that it creates an impression on other individuals (Robbins, 2015).

Based on previous research conducted by Ratna Puspitasari (2013) on employees of Matahari Department Store Cab. Pasar Besar in a study of 127 people proves that employees who have an extroverted personality type have higher organizational commitment than employees who have an introverted personality type.

And the results of research conducted by Amiruddin Aziz (2016) on the entire Military Army V Brawijaya prove that there are significant differences in the level of organizational commitment between extroverted and introverted personality types. Based on the background above, that personality type affects employee commitment in the organization. So in this case the researcher is interested in conducting research on "Differences in Organizational Commitment in View of Extroverted and Introverted Personality Types in Marketing Employees of PT Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang".

METHODS

This research is a non-experimental quantitative research used to research on certain populations or samples where data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses and to gain an understanding of the phenomenon or relationship between variables in a natural context and researchers make observations and collect data on the variables to be studied (Creswell & Creswell, 2022), but there is nothing to control or change existing conditions or variables. The variables used in this study can be classified into independent variables (X): Extroverted and Introverted personality types and dependent variable (Y): Organizational Commitment.

This research was conducted on May 2023 at PT Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang, a banking company established since 1958. The population and sample of this study were 100 marketing employees with total sampling technique. Organizational commitment data collection uses a Likert scale with 5 answer options, while personality type uses a Guttman scale with 2 options (a = extrovert, b = introvert). Validity and reliability tests use convergent validity and consistency reliability (Sugiyono, 2018).

Data analysis was conducted with the Independent Sample T-test to test the difference between the independent variable (personality type) and the dependent variable (organizational commitment). This study used a questionnaire as a data collection instrument and JASP (Jeffrey's Amazing Statistics Program) software for data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Assumption Test

a) Normality Testing

Table 1: Summary of Calculation Results of Normality Test Distribution

Variable	Group	Avg	S-W	SD	Sig	Notes
Organizational Commitment	Ekstroverted	192,706	0,735	17,549	0,051	Normal
	Introvert	160,061	0,717	60,107	0,061	Normal

The distribution normality test is carried out to prove the distribution of research data which is the center of attention. The normality test was analyzed using the research data normality test using the Shapiro-wilk technique. As a criterion if $p > 0.050$ the distribution is declared normal, otherwise it is stated if $p < 0.050$ the distribution is declared abnormal.

b) Homogenitas Testing

Table 2: Summary of Homogeneity Test Results

Variable	Homogenitas	Lavane Statistic	Sig (p)
Organizational Commitment	Levene Statistic	191,841	0,080

The homogeneity test was conducted to determine whether the research subjects were homogeneous. Based on the homogeneity test, it is known that the research subjects come from a homogeneous sample.

As a criterion if $p > 0.050$ the distribution is declared homogeneous, otherwise it is stated if $p < 0.050$ the distribution is declared not homogeneous.

The difference between the independent variable and the dependent variable in this study means whether differences in extroverted and introverted personality types will affect organizational commitment in marketing employees of PT Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang.

c) Hypothesis Testing

Table 3: Independent Samples T-Test

Organizational Commitment	Test	Statistic	df	p
	Student	3.718	98	< .001

Hypothesis testing was conducted to determine differences in organizational commitment based on extroverted and introverted personality types.

As a criterion if $p > 0.050$ the distribution is declared insignificant, otherwise if $p < 0.050$ the distribution is declared significant. Based on hypothesis testing, it is known that the criterion is $p < 0.001$, so the results are declared significant or there are differences in organizational commitment based on extroverted and introverted personality types.

d) Calculation of Hypothetical Mean and Empirical Mean

Table 4: Independent Samples T-Test

Variable	SD	Mean		Notes
		Hipotetik	Empirik	
Organizational Commitment x Extroverted	17,549	157,5	192,706	High
Organizational Commitment x Introvert	60,107	157,5	160,061	Medium

Based on the comparison of the two means above, the hypothetical mean and the empirical mean, it is known that marketing employees of PT Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang have high organizational commitment based on extroverted personality types compared to employees who have introverted personality types.

Comparison between the hypothetical mean and the empirical mean by paying attention to the SD value of the variable. For extroverted personality type organizational commitment, the SD value is 17.549, while for introverted personality type organizational commitment, the SD value is 60.107. Based on the comparison of the two means above, it is known that marketing employees of PT Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang have organizational commitment based on extroverted personality types compared to employees who have introverted personality types.

Then based on the comparison of the two hypothetical and empirical mean values, it is stated that the organizational commitment of marketing employees based on the extroverted personality type, the hypothetical mean is 112.5 less than the empirical mean of 192.706 where the difference exceeds the SD value of 17.549 and in marketing employees based on the introverted personality type, the hypothetical mean is 22.5 less than the empirical mean of 160.061, where the difference is more than the SD value of 60.107.

The results of data analysis using the Independent Sample T-test method, it is known that there is a significant difference between organizational commitment and the personality type of marketing employees of PT Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang. Based on the results of the T-test calculation, it can be seen that there is a significant difference between organizational commitment with extroverted and introverted personality types in marketing employees with the results of $p < 0.001$, meaning that based on the results of this study, it can be stated that there are differences in organizational commitment based on personality type in marketing employees at PT Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam Deli Serdang with the results of employees who have extroverted personality types, the higher the level of employee commitment to the organization compared to marketing employees who have introverted personality types.

DISCUSSION

Persons with extroverted personalities tend to have higher organizational commitment because they are more active and oriented towards the social environment, while introverts tend to be passive and less confident (Feist & Robert, 2018). Darmadi (2018) supports that personality affects the organizational commitment of marketing employees, having an impact on the progress of the company.

Ratna Puspitasari's (2011) study showed a significant difference between personality type and organizational commitment ($t = 2.141$; $p = 0.034$) in Matahari Department Store employees. Amiruddin Aziz (2016) found 70.5% of Indonesian Army members with high Big Five personality categories had greater organizational commitment.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

This study shows that marketing employees of PT Bank BTPN Lubuk Pakam with extroverted personalities have higher organizational commitment than introverted ones. Extroverted employees are more adaptable, confident, and active in social interactions, while introverted employees tend to be more passive and less confident. Understanding the personality of employees is very important to improve organizational commitment and performance.

Suggestions

1. Targeted Recruitment - Use personality tests in selection to match candidates with job demands.
2. Training and Development - Provide communication and confidence training for introverted employees.
3. Support and Motivation - Provide mentoring and social support to increase work comfort and commitment.
4. Task Adjustment - Customize roles based on personality, e.g. introverts on strategy analysis and extroverts on customer interaction.

References

- 1) Aziz, A. (2016). Perbedaan Tingkat Komitmen Organisasi Ditinjau dari Tipe Kepribadian Pada TNI AD Brawijaya. Undergraduate thesis, Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim, Malang.
- 2) Bae, S. (2023), "Evaluating hospitality employees' various relationships and the effects on organizational commitment", *International Hospitality Review*, Vol. 37 No. 2, pp. 202-218. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IHR-01-2021-0005>
- 3) Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2022). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- 4) Darmadi. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Kekepalasekolahan*. Penerbit Deepublish.
- 5) Farrukh, M., Ying, C.W. and Mansori, S. (2017), "Organizational commitment: an empirical analysis of personality traits", *Journal of Work-Applied Management*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 18-34. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JWAM-12-2016-0026>
- 6) Feist, J., Feist, G.J., Roberts, T.A. (2018). *Teori Kepribadian*. Jakarta: Salemba Humanika.
- 7) Fitri Anggreani, T. (2021). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Swot: Strategi Pengembangan Sdm, Strategi Bisnis, Dan Strategi MSDM (Suatu Kajian Studi Literatur Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia). *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Sistem Informasi*, 2(5 SE-Articles), 619–629. <https://doi.org/10.31933/jemsi.v2i5.588>

- 8) Karlinda, A. E., Nadilla, N., & Sopali, M. F. (2022). Dukungan Organisasi, Keadilan Organisasi dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Batanghari Barisan Padang. *Jurnal Ekobistek*, 11(2SE-Artikel), 73–78. <https://doi.org/10.35134/ekobistek.v11i2.318>
- 9) Kurniawan, H. (2022). Literature Review: Analisis Kinerja Pegawai Melalui Komitmen Organisasi Kompensasi dan Motivasi. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Sistem Informasi*, 3(4 SE-Articles), 426–441. <https://doi.org/10.31933/jemsi.v3i4.966>
- 10) Muktamar, A., & Saputra, A. (2024). Mengungkap Peran Vital Kepemimpinan dalam Manajemen SDM: Produktivitas, Kepuasan Kerja, dan Retensi Tenaga Kerja yang Berkualitas. *Journal of International Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(2 SE-Articles), 9–19. <https://doi.org/10.62504/1nv76056>
- 11) Puspitsari, R. (2013). Perbedaan Komitmen Organisasi Ditinjau dari Tipe Kepribadian. Skripsi Tidak Dipublikasikan. Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang: Malang.
- 12) Robbins, S. (2015). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: Penerbit Salemba Empat.
- 13) Sakti, S. H., Ikhsan, M., Abdoellah, M. N., Zabidi, I., & Anggara, A. (2023). Pengaruh rekrutmen SDM, penempatan dan komitmen kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan PT LT di Jakarta. *Jurnal Riset Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 8(1 SE-Articles). <https://doi.org/10.36407/jrmb.v8i1.1036>
- 14) Spector, B. (2013). *Implementing Organizational Change*. USA: Pearson Education.
- 15) Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Bisnis : Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, Kombinasi dan R&D*. Alfabeta.
- 16) Wijaya, C., dan Rifa'i, M. (2016). *Dasar-dasar Manajemen*. Medan: Perdana Publishing.